

Information System Management Factors Related to Behavioral Trend of Online Accommodation Services

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Abstract—The purpose of this research was to study the customers' behavioral trend for online accommodation system at Bangkonthi District, Samutsongkhram province. The research collected data from 400 online users. A questionnaire was utilized as the tool in collecting information. Descriptive statistics included frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Independent-sample t- test, analysis of variance and Pearson Correlation were also used. The findings of this research revealed that the majority of the respondents were male, 25-32 years old, and graduated a bachelor degree. The respondents mostly worked in private sectors and had monthly income between 10,001-15,000 baht. The regular online users, visiting this system between 3-4 times/month, spending 1-2 hours/time, searched for online accommodation information. This result showed that the users had good and high attitude towards the system. According to the hypothesis testing, the number of online usage had positive related to the behavioral trends: accommodation purchasing intention and recommend the accommodation to others. Furthermore, both the number of online usage and overall attitude had a significant correlation to accommodation purchase intention and recommend the accommodation to others.

Keywords—Customer Behavior, Information System Management, Online Accommodation Services.

I. INTRODUCTION

TOURISM industry is a category of fields within the service business which is very important to the economic system of Thailand. Tourism is a main source of income to developing countries. When tourists spend foreign currency, this may help to increase developments in the country and thereby accelerates economic growth. Income from tourism are added to the national income and this leads to improvements of infrastructure, public services such as hospitals, schools and even tourist accommodations, which will in turn bring more tourists and thus increasing the national income to a further extent. In 2012, the growth of the tourism industry in Thailand about 16% over the last year and generate more passive income 1,038.7 billion baht [1].

A thriving tourism industry supports the growth in other sectors, one of which is accommodation business. Accommodation business is one of the most important sections of the tourism industry [2] that contributes to overall tourism income and be related to tourists directly because the tourists require a location where they can rest during their travels, or a place to stay when arriving at a tourism destination. When tourism industry is a rapidly growing, there

are more opportunities for accommodation business to develop. The development of accommodation has accompanied the growth of tourism locations, relative to the demand for visiting a local tourism attraction. In Thailand, tourism continues to be an increasingly attractive for improving the economies of small cities and towns because people travel more today than ever before. Developing the local tourism industry make sense for small communities to get an opportunity to serve needs and capture a share of traveler spending. A few years ago many small towns have improved more and more of accommodation for local tourism industry. The entrepreneur in small towns has tended to invest in a small accommodation that service with outstanding attention and create an impressive atmosphere for the guests [3] like resort and homestay continuously because ease of management, low initial investment, easy to make the difference, not necessary to report environment impact [4].

Bangkonthi district is located in Samutsongkhram province, Thailand, where has a variety of tourist attraction such as cultural areas, historical sites and natural attractions. These tourism locations are a valuable resource to support to provide income to communities. The major tourism activities are include watching the firefly, visiting temples and shrines, studying the way of life and sightseeing along canals. To support tourism, many accommodations have been developed in Bangkonthi district, especially homestays that because the rising demand by tourists for experiential tourism. Mostly location of tourist accommodation is situated near the riverside, which is very beautiful sightseeing. At homestays, tourists can lives, eats, and shares the majority of his/her time in the host family which provides a total experience. When has more accommodation it effect to more competition so each entrepreneur tried to find approach to increase competitive advantage. The one of most is the online accommodation information system due to the important role of this system is the use of it as a marketing tool. Before accommodation businesses offer information, promotion and services it has to set up its own online information system so the entrepreneur or developer have to apply satisfactory information, attractive designs and offer guests a virtual tour of the entire property and show various room types. These strategies are considered a minor but may get a lot of appeal from online users. The internet also allows accommodation businesses to reach more customers by using search engine optimization, which is a tool that helps increasing page ranking in search engine results. Another online marketing strategy for the accommodation businesses is online customer

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relationship management, which are activities to manage the relationships between customers and the entrepreneur by using the internet and web browsers. Moreover, CRM helps the accommodation businesses know more about their online information system visitors and also helps to identify their customers and their travel planning and purchasing behavior.

From the above information, to study about Information System Management Factors that Related to Behavioral Trend of Online Accommodation Services at Bangkonthi district Samutsongkhram province to analyze the approach for improving the online information system is very interesting.

II. METHODOLOGY

The objectives of this study were: 1) To study the behavioral trend for online accommodation system at Bangkonthi, Samutsongkhram province by classifying the demographic factors 2) Study the relationship between online usage behavior and the behavioral trend for online accommodation system at Bangkonthi, Samutsongkhram province.

The Research Hypotheses were: 1) The online users whose different in demographic factors will have a different effect on their behavioral trend 2) Online usage behavior would relate to the behavioral trend for online accommodation system at Bangkonthi, Samutsongkhram province.

The theory of behavioral trend from Schiffman and Kanuk (1994) [5] and the variable was considered as "Information management system" based on the idea of Govere, Tsokota, Chikuta, Mukwembi, and Chinofunga (2013) [6] have been applied in this research framework.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

The sample of this research was online users at 9 online information systems of accommodation businesses at Bangkonthi, Samutsongkhram province in March 2013. The random samples are 400 sampling. In this study, quota sampling and a convenient sampling were used to portion the

samples of online user from each online accommodation system as shown in Table I.

TABLE I
 NUMBER OF SAMPLE

	Department	Number of sampling (set)
1	http://www.suansangtawan.com/	45
2	http://www.baansuanlynchee.com/	44
3	http://www.kusumahomestay.com/	44
4	http://www.bang-onhomestay.com/	45
5	http://www.baansuankunyay.com/	45
6	http://www.baansuanrak.com/	44
7	http://www.baansuansaitong.com/	45
8	http://www.baanchidchol.com/	44
9	http://www.manovejchaphan.com/	44
Total		400

III. FINDINGS

The results of this study revealed that the majority of the online users were male between 25-32 years old, single status, bachelor degree holder and working for private companies. The average income of the users was 10,001- 15,000 baht per month. These users accessed to online accommodation information system about 3-4 times per month and spent online were about 1-2 hours per time. The mostly users searched for online information system before they decided where they wanted to stay. The main reasons for searching online information system included access and compare the detailed information more easily.

The hypothesis testing disclosed that online users with different demographic had different the behavioral trend. Furthermore, high correlations between behaviors of using online information system per month with the trend of purchase intention. This can be explained that searching or accessing per month had increased; therefore, the user's purchase intention will be higher. Beside this, medium correlations between behaviors of searching for online accommodation system per month with the trend of recommended the accommodation to others. Moreover, the attitude to online information management had high correlations with behavioral trends of intending purchase and recommended to others. Dimension of online information management include accommodation information dimension, tourist attractions dimension, tourism events dimension, communication dimension, transaction dimension, customer relationship dimension, system management dimension, system designing dimension, link to other dimension and privacy dimension show in the same high level direction.

IV. DISCUSSION

1. The analysis of correlating online usage behavior and behavioral trend of accommodation business usage at Bangkonthi district, Samutsongkhram province found that the spending behavior had effects to intending to purchase and recommended the accommodation to others, which is consistent with Yulihastri, Md. Aminul Islam,

and Ku Amir Ku (2011) . The finding of this study discovered that the behavior of using internet per week and length of use in years correlated with behavioral trend of intending of shopping online [7].

2. This study showed that the overall attitude to online accommodation information management at Bangkonthi district, Samutsongkhram province and each dimension of online information management include accommodation information, tourist attractions, tourism events, communication, transaction, customer relationship, system management, system designing, link to other and privacy are related with behavioral trend in intending to purchase and recommended to others, indicated overall attitude had a significance in Statistic, which concurred with Mohd Fazli Mohd Sam, and Md Nor Hayati Tahir (2009). The findings of this study revealed that the attitude to website: quality of data, designing and customer relationship management had related with customer's purchase intention [8].

V. RECOMMENDATION

1. The majority of online users for online accommodation systems were male, the aged of 25-32 years old with the bachelor's degree and had monthly income between 10,001-15,000 baht whose searched for the systems before they decided where they wanted to stay. The entrepreneur can use this data to build marketing plan for specific target group to get more market share.
2. The attitude of online users to information system management of online accommodation services in accommodation information dimension, tourist attraction dimension ,tourism events dimension, communication dimension and behavior of purchase intention had correlated therefore these dimensions can be the strong point of online accommodation services at Bangkonthi District, Samutsongkhram province. The entrepreneur or system developer should be acutely aware of these dimensions, especially, the diversity of presented information. This will increase behavioral trend in purchase intention and recommended the accommodation to others.
3. The findings revealed also that attitude in terms of accommodation information are very important. Therefore, the entrepreneur or system developer of accommodation services at Bangkonthi District, Samutsongkhram province should provide clear and up-to-date information about their accommodation and services such as location of accommodation, room detail, price, facility, Rights and rules , route maps ,public transportation, food and service etc. to support decision making of users.
4. The findings revealed also that the attitude in terms of communication dimension is very important because communication channels are the methods used to send a message between users and entrepreneur. Therefore, the

entrepreneur or system developer of accommodation services at Bangkonthi District, Samutsongkhram province should provide multi communication channels such as telephone number, electronic mail, webboard, forum, etc. to offer the users can select the most appropriate means of conveying a message.

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